

Anal Fissures: A Case Series Study on How Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing Protocols Treated This Condition and Associated Symptoms

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ABSTRACT: Introduction: An anal fissure manifests as a painful longitudinal tear in the anoderm distal to the dentate line with symptoms of pain during defecation, rectal bleeding, tremendous emotional stress, and declined quality of life. Anal fissures are found more frequently in women. Several treatment options are available with or without medication and/or surgery. This paper presents 4 cases of patients affected by anal fissures healed by one healer and cured successfully by the application of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healing protocols as alternative medicine.

Method: This paper uses the case study method by collecting medical data from the 4 patients (3 female and 1 male), YPV healer's records, and patient feedback.

Results: Patient in case 1 became normal after 37 healing sessions of 20 minutes each in 1 ½ months of YPV healing. The patient in case 2 became normal after 25 sessions of 20 minutes of YPV healing conducted in 17 days. The patient in case 3 became normal after 35 sessions of 20 minutes each within a period of about 7 weeks of healing. The patient in case 4 became normal after 10 sessions of 20 minutes of healing within 11 days.

Conclusions: This paper presented multiple cases of anal fissures suffered by patients over many years that have been cured successfully by the application of the integrated and holistic system of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healing protocols. Further research is recommended. Recommendations include training Healthcare workers for applying YPV techniques complementary to their respective professions for treating patients holistically and as a preventive modality boosting immunity.

KEYWORDS: Anal fissures, Constipation, Yoga Prana Vidya System ®, YPV®

INTRODUCTION

Anorectal disorders including fissures and hemorrhoids are among the most common afflictions of people in India, negatively impacting the 'quality of life' of the patient. Clinicians observe that the prevalence of anorectal disorders in the general population is probably much higher than what is seen in clinical practice, and most of the patients hesitate to seek medical care unless the symptoms become too bothersome [1].

Anal fissures affect both men and women and are common in all age groups, especially young people. Despite advancement and extensive research, the exact etiology of anal fissures is still unknown. The possible reasons include trauma to the anus caused during the defecation of hard stools. Food habits such as a low-fiber diet are also considered to be contributory factors for the occurrence of anal fissures [1]. A study by Chaudhary et al. (2019) found that the prevalence of anal fissures among patients with anorectal complaints was around 18% [1].

Anal fissures are tears in the anal canal accompanied by pain, bleeding, and spasms. Many patients may not require surgery; hence they can be treated with non-surgical options such as sitz baths, local anaesthetics, topical nitrates, oral fiber, calcium channel blockers, etc. Topical nitrates have side effects such as severe headaches, while topical calcium channel blockers can cause itching. There is a need to explore alternative treatments with fewer or no side effects[2]. A study by Gopalakrishna et al. (2023) evaluated the efficacy of ayurvedic treatment with some success [2]. Their findings suggested the need for further research with alternatives. A previous study by Iyer et al. (2023) revealed a successful application of Yoga Prana Vidya protocols in the treatment of chronic anal fissures [3]. A literature search shows over 90 published research articles on YPV system healing protocols that include experimental interventional studies, and case reports of various types of illnesses and diseases healed successfully. This paper presents 4 separate cases of anal fissures completely healed by one Healer as shown in Table 1.

CASE REPORT

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Details of the YPV Healer:

The healer who treated the 4 cases reported in this paper was a Mumbai based Associate Certified YPV Healer & YPV Level 1 Trainer, a female homemaker aged 52, and has experience of more than 10 years in the practice of Yoga Prana Vidya Energy Healing.

The profile of the patients in this study is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Patients' profile

S.no	Gender	Age	Occupation	Pre-YPV condition	Result after YPV intervention
1	Female	26	Software	Constipation and Anal fissures in the past 11 years.	Became normal in 1 ½ months, 37 sessions of 20 minutes each
2	Female	26	Accountant	Weakness and unbearable pain in her lower body & Trouble from fissures for 2 past years	Normal in 17 days of healing, 25 sessions of 20 minutes each
3	Female	50	Housewife	Severe weakness, back pain, pain in the hip region & legs, trouble from fissures for 3 past years	Normal in about 7 weeks of healing, 35 sessions of 20 minutes each
4	Male	36	Tax Consultant	Chronic constipation and fissures in the past 10 years	Normal in 11 days of healing, 10 sessions of 20 minutes each

The YPV Healing protocols used by the healer for all 4 cases cited in Table 1 of this report are as stated below.

1. Physical and psychological healing, blood cleansing, internal organ cleansing, and organ regeneration - done normally once a day.
 2. Healing the patient's affected part normally twice a day with a special protocol to reduce the pain in the affected part.
 3. Changing the etheric environment of their house and office by blessing, salt water mobbing, and using incense stick.
- The YPV healer in addition prescribed some self-practice modules to the patients as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Suggested Self-practice YPV protocols followed by patients

S.no	Gender	Practices done by patient
1	Female	Rhythmic yogic breathing and forgiveness sadhana twice or thrice a day.
2	Female	Rhythmic yogic breathing and forgiveness sadhana once or twice a day. 10 am Divine Group healing session. Blessings.
3	Female	No practices were done by her.
4	Male	Rhythmic Yogic Breathing and Forgiveness Sadhana three times a day, and as and when he had pain. Soul Affirmation. Erasing unwholesome thoughts as and when they arise by using erasing technique taught. Also, whenever he had to use the washroom, he used to inform the healer and received preventive healing as well from the healer.

The following paragraphs narrate each case of healing in detail and the results obtained.

paragraphs

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CASE 1

Patient details: Female aged 26 years, Occupation: software developer, based in Mumbai.

Condition before YPV:

The patient had fissures since she was 12 years old. For fissures, she consulted different doctors which included allopathy, ayurvedic, and homeopathy. She tried home remedies also. But nothing concrete was achieved with all the different treatments in the preceding 11 years. So, now she was not taking any medications and was trying to increase her water intake and consume food that was cool for the body.

During her school and college days, she somehow managed things, but the issue aggravated when she started working after completing her engineering in 2018. Late night work, long sitting hours, a sedentary lifestyle, changes in food habits, and improper timing of food all together aggravated the situation.

Sometimes blood was seen while passing stool, and the pain, and burning sensation had become unbearable such that once the pain and burning started, she could not sit for more than 5 to 6 hours. Consequently, explaining this situation every time in the office was getting very uncomfortable for her. Sometimes she used to get a fever associated with extreme pricking pain and burning sensation.

YPV intervention & results:

Through a common friend, she came to know that Yoga Prana Vidya healing can help her in this situation, so she approached the YPV healer. At that time along with fissures (with symptoms of bleeding, pricking pain, burning sensation & fever), she felt numbness in her left cheek, chin, and neck areas due to a two-month-old dental surgery. So, the healer started healing her for fissures and for numbness on her left cheek.

YPV healing was started on 17th February 2020 when the patient visited the healer. As the healing progressed, her discomfort was gradually reducing. After going through a healing session of 15 to 20 mins the patient was able to sit and felt relaxed. The patient was pleased with the improvements and joined training classes in the next two days and learned the Yoga Prana Vidya Level 1 healing course along with her mother. Even on the day of class she was again having a lot of pain after passing stool she was not able to move, so she immediately called the healer and explained the entire situation. The healer then healed her and in the next 10 mins she informed the healer that she was able to stand and walk and she will join the class in next few minutes. She was able to walk for 7 to 8 minutes to join the class.

After 2 days of healing, the patient was feeling a little better, the pain was reduced a little and there was no fever.

On 21st February 2020 after five healings her pain, burning sensation, bleeding, and discomfort while sitting reduced to around 60%, felt much more comfortable and relaxed. Even she got a sensation back around 20% in her left cheek. Overall, she felt more energetic throughout the day.

On 8th March 2020 after eight healings, her fissure pain, burning sensation, and bleeding were reduced by 95%. She said she was feeling much better and happy as she could go to the office and attend all the meetings with ease. Also, her left cheek regained complete sensitivity during this period. On 31st March 2020 after twenty healings, she felt nearly normal.

During the entire intervention, the patient was practicing rhythmic yogic breathing and forgiveness sadhana twice or thrice a day. The patient experienced full relief after a total of 37 healing sessions, each of 20 minutes duration.

A follow-up during the succeeding 3 years revealed that the patient experienced no relapse of fissures. The patient confirmed that an ordeal of 11 years of struggles with different medications to treat fissures ended successfully with YPV healing intervention within a few months without any use of medication.

CASE 2

Patient details: Female aged 26 years, Occupation: Accountant, resident in Mumbai.

Pre-YPV condition:

The patient experienced fissures after her first child was born in 2018 and then it continued intermittently. But it aggravated when she resumed her office on 29th September 2020 after her maternity leave. Due to this, she was not able to sit, also there was burning, pricking pain, cuts in the anus areas, and blood in the stool. She was very scared because it was not subsiding and the pain was unbearable.

Along with fissures she had weakness and unbearable pain in her lower body. Due to this, she was not able to spend some quality time with her baby daughter. She felt very sad and guilty about the fact that her physical body was not fit enough to balance her professional and family life.

For fissures, she was not taking any medications and just was trying to increase water intake and consume fibrous foods, and for weakness, she did not take any medicines.

YPV intervention & results:

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Through a mutual contact, the patient approached the YPV healer for healing. The patient herself being a YPV healer Level 1, was regularly doing forgiveness sadhana and rhythmic yogic breathing on her own once or twice a day.

On 1st October 2020 after three healings her pain reduced and she could attend the office and was able to sit continuously for 8 to 9 hours. Her weakness was reduced by almost 80 to 85% and she completed her work in less time than before because she also felt a lot of stress energy had been released from her system. A lot of guilt and lack of forgiveness had been reduced., making her feel more relaxed and stress-free.

On 7th October 2020 after a total of 6 healings, she experienced little pain and bleeding, though bearable without disturbing her work.

On 17th October 2020 after total of 25 healings the pain stopped completely and there was no more discomfort regarding fissures. She was feeling normal and could do her routine work with much ease. The patient experienced pain relief besides feeling emotionally strong and confident.

The patient felt very happy with the improvements in her health both physically and emotionally. A follow-up during the succeeding years revealed that there was no recurrence of fissures. In this intervention, the results were achieved with a total of 25 healings, each of 20 mins duration.

CASE 3

Patient details: female of age 50 years, a housewife, resident in Mumbai.

Pre-YPV condition:

The patient was suffering from piles for the past 3 years and was unable to afford regular treatment due to financial issues. In these 3 years, she tried taking some remedial treatments unsuccessfully. The pain became very unbearable and each time she had to lie down for one or two days to feel better. She used to take some painkillers to ease her condition at that time.

YPV intervention:

The patient then approached this YPV healer around the 7th of March 2020 through a known contact narrating the ordeals she was going through. The patient confided with the healer that, in addition to having unbearable pain in the anus area, some part was seen coming out of the anus while passing stool (rectal prolapse) which she had to put back in with her hands. There was also blood seen in her stool, accompanied by a burning sensation and too much weakness, her eyes and face looking pale. She then consulted a doctor as she had severe weakness & pain in her lower back, hip, and legs. Also, her weakness was increasing day by day. Looking at her condition, the doctor suggested multivitamins as there were high chances of calcium, vitamin D, and haemoglobin deficiency. Due to the prevailing COVID situation, things were more difficult than before due to the risk of infection, so they decided to continue with the current medication only apart from YPV healings.

On 15th March 2020 after 7 healings her piles' pain got lower than before, and it subsided completely after 5 – 6 hrs of healing. During that time, she was able to work unlike in earlier times, and managed to sleep though not able to lie down with ease.

On 23rd March 2020 after 14 healings her feeling of getting drained reduced by 35 - 40%. Her face and eyes looked livelier.

On 12th April 2020 after 28 healings, her symptoms of pain of piles, bleeding and rectal prolapse healed completely.

On 29th April 2020 after 35 healings the patient was told no more need for any medications. She was declared completely recovered from piles and associated other symptoms.

After concluding the healing intervention which was conducted for about 7 weeks with a total of 35 healing sessions each of 20 minutes duration, she never had a recurrence of issues of piles in the following years, as stated by the patient during regular follow-ups between May 2020 to June 2023.

CASE 4

Patient details: Male aged 36 years, a Tax consultant, and resident of Mumbai.

Pre-YPV condition:

The patient was having pain while passing stool for the past 15 days. He contacted this healer for healing on 21st February 2022. The symptoms were pain, burning sensation, difficulty in sitting and passing stool. The patient was on a liquid diet for the last two days before he contacted the healer for healing.

The patient started practicing the Suggested YPV protocols as given in Table 2:

5.

On 24th February 2022, after 4 healings, the bleeding stopped but the pain was still there. The patient felt difficulty sitting and walking and felt hurt while passing stool.

Within the next 5 healings on 28th February 2022, his pain had reduced by 30% and it only pained for a few hours after passing stool. The hardness near the anus has been reduced by 70%.

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Within the next 5 healings by 3rd March 2022, the burning, pain, hardness, bleeding, and constipation and all associated symptoms vanished and the patient was back to normal condition with the usual diet.

In this process, his problem of indigestion also got completely cured. Earlier he had to skip meals due to which he used to have headaches and uneasiness. While healing his fissures, all other issues of the past 10 years, such as digestion, assimilation & elimination got resolved. In this YPV intervention, a total of 10 healing sessions each of 20 minutes in duration were conducted.

DISCUSSION

An anal fissure is a common anorectal problem, which is a painful longitudinal tear in the anoderm distal to the dentate line. The patients are usually diagnosed upon presenting the symptoms such as significant pain during defecation with a variable amount of rectal bleeding. Along with physical pain, this condition can result in tremendous emotional stress, which causes an overall decline in the quality of life of a person. Usually, anal fissures are found more frequently in women. While the acute anal fissure often heals within 1–2 weeks, chronic anal fissures are less likely to heal even after 6–8 weeks of medical management. Medical treatment of anal fissures is focused on reducing the pressure of the internal sphincter muscle with the help of physical or chemical methods, and the treatment strategy for chronic anal fissures varies from conservative medical management to surgery [4].

The guidelines of the American Society of Colon and Rectal Surgeons (ASCRS) recommend that for the initial nonsurgical management of anal fissure, the patient should be recommended stool softeners, a high-fiber diet, and a warm sitz bath. However, with the application of pharmacological agents, the success rate (65–75%) of this treatment strategy is significantly lower than as observed in surgical treatment [5].

Home remedies for anal fissures generally recommended include sitz baths, fiber supplements, stool softeners, and adequate hydration and fiber intake [6].

A research report shows that two major factors, the increasing elderly population, and unhealthy lifestyles, are driving the anal fissure treatment needs globally. Increasing constipation rates are expected to propel the anal fissure treatment needs going forward. Constipation is a condition characterized by hard, dry, and difficult-to-pass stools and infrequent bowel motions. Constipation that causes pain, as well as feeling bloated, uneasy, and lethargic, are possible signs. Anus lining damage, which most frequently occurs in constipated patients, leads to anal fissures, requiring treatment [7].

Literature shows that the Yoga Prana Vidya System, which fosters a healthy lifestyle for people of all age groups, consists of integrated protocols with holistic benefits to the users and practitioners without the use of medicines or touch. This touchless and drugless energy healing system has been found to have worked effectively as complementary and alternative medicine treating a wide range of diseases as is evident from over 90 published research articles [8]. It is further observed that YPV healing therapies include psychotherapy tools to help the patient overcome anxiety and depression and maintain emotional and mental balance while facing the challenges of diseases and undergoing treatment processes that sometimes need longer-term sustained healing treatments [9]. A previous study by Iyer et al. (2023) revealed one 32-year-old female patient's case with chronic anal fissures that occurred soon after the delivery of her child and could not find relief with any other modality such as allopathic, ayurvedic, or homeopathic. She tried allopathic treatments but had to stop soon as the symptoms only worsened. She then switched to ayurvedic treatment. Though it helped initially, the fissures came back after a year and only were partially cured. As the fissures came back fully after two years, she eventually stopped Ayurvedic treatment too. She tried homeopathy treatment and found a little relief. Finally, Iyer's treatment using Yoga Prana Vidya protocols gave successful results with no relapse reported during the follow-up in the succeeding 3 years [3].

It is further observed in the literature that there are several other cases related to gastrointestinal system diseases, besides some difficult medical cases [10] successfully cured using Yoga Prana Vidya system protocols including Reflux esophagitis [11], Esophageal cancer stage 2 [12], Gastroesophageal malignancy [13], Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease [14], and irritable bowel syndrome [15].

CONCLUSIONS

It is observed from this study that multiple cases of anal fissures have been cured by the application of the integrated and holistic system of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) protocols by a qualified and experienced YPV healer. Further research is recommended using appropriate sample and methodology. Recommendations include training Healthcare workers to apply YPV techniques complementary to their respective professions for treating patients holistically, and also as a preventive modality boosting immunity.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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